

Registration of the trademark of the Szekler Product and development of the control methodology, organisation of monthly fairs in Harghita County

Problem encountered and objective

Harghita County Council identified that small producers struggled with market access, inspection-related fears, and low consumer awareness, prompting the creation of monthly local product fairs and the Székely Termék Trademark with clear quality standards. Control authorities were brought directly to the fairs to advise farmers, reducing mistrust and improving compliance, supported by around €40,000 annually and later expanded through EU projects. Over time, the County Development Agency took over fair and trademark management, while an NGO now oversees trademark control, with regular producer visits and continuous monitoring of consumer needs.

Main results / outcomes

Stronger cooperation between farmers and institutions; increased consumer trust and awareness; professionalisation of local producers; a recognised trademark ensuring quality; and sustainable structures for fair organisation and support. Markets are held every second Saturday in the county seat (Miercurea Ciuc), and for several years now, monthly markets have been held on the first Saturday in Gherogheni and on the last Saturday in Odorheiu Secuiesc, the county's two other major regions. The process engaged around 200 farmers, public institutions, Sapientia University, and farmers' organisations. Farmers must meet a set of criteria in order to be granted the right to use the logo, and compliance is checked annually.

Practical recommendations

Local governments must remain politically sensitive to farmers' needs, cooperate continuously with inspection bodies and academia, and adapt to emerging opportunities by monitoring consumer habits. In Romania's context —where no specific legislation on local products exists— county-level leadership and flexible collaboration are essential for supporting small producers, as demonstrated by Harghita County's moderating role between producers and licensing authorities. Producers must meet strict requirements to use the Szekler Product Logo, for which they receive targeted training.

Further information

<https://szekelytermek.ro>

About this abstract

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